

Mahabharat and Subaltern Revival

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Abstract The Mahabharata, a cornerstone of Indian literature, transcends its role as an epic to critique social hierarchies and advocate for inclusivity. This paper examines the subaltern revival within the Mahabharata, highlighting the determination of marginalized figures such as Vyasa, Vidura, and Ekalavya, alongside the strong and resilient characters of women often dismissed as the weaker sex. Through their narratives, the text challenges caste-based discrimination and underscores the primacy of merit, character, and dharma over birth and privilege. By deconstructing dominant Brahmanical ideologies, the Mahabharata emerges as a timeless commentary on social justice and human potential. Its enduring relevance extends into postcolonial discourses, enriching modern debates on equality, representation, cultural pluralism, and subaltern agency.

Keywords Matriarchal, marginalized, Feminist, Dharma, Caste, Brahminical.

Introduction

Epics and myths in India have always been integral to the cultural ethos of the nation. They have perennially been vehicles of political, social, or spiritual messages in contexts demanding the promulgation of the respective discourse. Consequently, these tales of the yore have generated multiple narratives and perspectives that often counter each other. (1).

The Sanskrit epic *Mahabharata* is widely regarded by historians of Early India as a valuable source of historical insight. Its composition is broadly dated between c. 400 BCE and c. 400 CE. A critical study of this monumental text provides a window into the political ideas and social institutions of a period extending roughly from c. 500 BCE to 500 CE.

The *Mahabharata*, a work of extraordinary depth, offers timeless reflections on the values, dilemmas, and stories of ancient India. The Mahabharata, both literally and figuratively, is the 'Great Indian Story'.(2) Mahabharata, the illustrious book that speaks of our times of yore, reflects greatly upon the society that lived then, their social institutions, norms, and customs. While reading the Mahabharata, one realizes that these three aspects of society are very closely intertwined. However, what is most intriguing are the changes that take place in the society. Some norms become more rigid with time while some may just fade away. Social change doesn't just happen all of a sudden; it is a slow and gradual process that takes place with the changes in the ideas and beliefs of people that take long to alter.

Objective of study This paper examines the subaltern revival within the Mahabharata, highlighting the determination of marginalized figures such as Vyasa, Vidura, and Ekalavya, alongside the strong and resilient characters of women often dismissed as the weaker sex.

Review of Literature

Women of the epic

Postcolonial feminist readings on the actions and responses of the mythical, epic women in the *Mahabharata* approve of the matriarchal culture that prevailed in ancient India. Indian women have traditionally been regarded as powerful entities, the source of life and energy. Both the *Ramayana* and the *Mahabharata* relate instances of outstanding women who demonstrate striking features of femininity that enable them to overcome their marginalized status.

Epic women in the *Mahabharata* like Satyavati, Kunti, and Draupadi present this modern concept of strikingly individualistic feminine consciousness or “female culture” that, as Gerda Lerner states, exists within the “general culture” of men and women. (3)

“Women live their social existence within the general culture and, whenever they are confined by patriarchal restraint or segregation into separateness (which always has subordination as its purpose), they transform this restraint into complementarity (asserting the importance of woman’s function, even its ‘superiority’) and redefine it. Thus, women live a duality—as members of the general culture and as partakers of women’s culture.”(4)

The most striking instance of social exclusion may be witnessed in the character of Satyavati (also called *Kali* for having black complexion) herself. Satyavati agrees to the demands of the sage Parashara for sexual union on condition that her virginity would remain intact, that she would lose her fishy odor and be blessed with eternal youth like Helen (the most beautiful woman in Greek mythology), and that her illegitimate son Vyasa would be a renowned man (5). Satyavati later marries Santanu, the King of Hastinapura, on the condition that her heirs would inherit the kingdom instead of her stepson Devavrata (Bhishm). Afterward, when Vichitravirya, the younger son from Santanu and Satyavati, dies without an heir, she unhesitatingly commands her illegitimate son Vyasa to impregnate Vichitravirya’s widows following the *Niyoga* (an ancient, socially accepted custom used to proliferate the family line in which a woman whose husband had died or could not have a child would take the help of another man in bearing a child). Thus, the aristocratic Kuru dynasty was replaced by the Nishada race propagated through Satyavati and Vyasa. Satyavati transcends the limitations of her birth as a low-caste woman and displays exceptional shrewdness, keen sense of diplomacy, and political acumen to emerge triumphant over the ruling Kurus to secure for herself and her descendants the right to the throne of Hastinapura. Kunti conceiving children out of wedlock, and still being ordained a place of respect; Draupadi engaging in polyandry with no major stigma.

Amba was a beautiful princess of Kashi and was on the verge of marrying her beloved, Salwa, but at the last minute, all her dreams were shattered when Bhishma forcibly took her along with her two sisters to get her married to his stepbrother Vichitra Veerya. She was sent back to her lover who had rejected her, and she was again rejected by Bhishma when she returned. Her life thus turns into a tragedy and she rightly blames Bhishma for his atrocity.

The contemporary relevance is that no woman should be forced to marry a person whom she does not select herself. Due freedom shall be given to girls to select their husbands. The acceptance of Shikhandi and Arjun exploring his feminine side as Brihannala are themes that can rile many even in the 21st Century.

Kunti not only looked after her sons after Pandu's death but also created incomparable warriors who were brave and conscientious at the same time. She inspires her sons not to be complacent but to fight for their kingdom. The Kunti in the *Mahabharata* never prays for perpetual afflictions she asserts— (O sons, I have enjoyed my husband's kingship amply, offered charity on a grand scale, and drunk soma to my satisfaction.) So she tells her sons that she inspired them to fight not for her happiness but for their own meaningful life according to dharma. This is her positive attitude towards life that befits a Kshatriya woman to resist the usurpers, and it also befits the heroic age to which the epic belongs. (6)

Draupadi stands as a heroine with few parallels in world literature. Her universal appeal lies in her exceptional beauty, unwavering dignity, remarkable forbearance, and sharp intelligence. Her character has consistently posed a creative challenge to writers across generations, inspiring them to explore her multifaceted persona. To modern women, Draupadi represents a powerful figure who demanded justice, not mercy, in the court of the Kauravas. Vyasa's depiction of her beauty is as follows: (7) (She was born from the altar of a yajna. Her eyes were like lotus petals and her body was comely, flawless, and delicate. She was high-minded and proud manasvini and a fragrance, like that of a blue lotus, was wafting gently around her.)

Gerda Lerner mentions some characteristics of feminist consciousness in her *The Creation of Patriarchy*. Some of them are 1) awareness of a wrong 2) development of a sense of sisterhood 3) autonomous definition by women of their goals and 4) strategies for changing their condition. (8)

Several women in the *Mahabharata*, such as Shakuntala, display boldness and frankness in asserting their desires, including for sexual happiness—a subject traditionally taboo in Indian culture. Ganga approaches Prateepa with a direct declaration of her desire to

marry him, while Sharmishtha makes a similar plea to Yayati, leading to their eventual marriage.

Additionally, the epic highlights a recurring theme of marginalization associated with dark-skinned characters, often portrayed as being outside the Vedic community. Notable among them are Satyawati, Vyasa, Krishna, Arjuna, and Draupadi, all of whom hold pivotal roles in the narrative. Krishna, for instance, emerges as a transformative figure, leading marginalized groups to challenge entrenched power structures. In his youth, Krishna mobilizes the Yadava cowherds to rise against the Kshatriya rulers of Mathura, ultimately overthrowing and killing the tyrant Kansa. Later, he becomes the guiding force for the five Pandavas, whom Duryodhana dismisses as "outsiders" for not being direct descendants of Pandu, aiding them in their struggle against the Kauravas. Through Krishna, the Mahabharata repeatedly underscores the empowerment of the less privileged to challenge and dismantle the ruling elite.

Draupadi's unique position in the epic is deeply rooted in her divine origins. As a reincarnation of Shri, Vishnu's consort, she carries a celestial aura. Her polyandrous marriage to the five Pandavas is imbued with divine legitimacy, stemming from a previous birth in which she implored Shiva five times for a husband. Consequently, her union with the Pandavas is seen as the fulfillment of this divine decree.

Main Text

Dharma and Caste in the Mahabharata

The Mahabharata is peopled by the 'higher' castes but there are important personages from the 'lower' castes whose presence gives a radical salience to 'dharma' as set out in the epic, to the point of even suggesting a subversion of the dominant ideology. (9)

The caste system had not yet become very rigid. We get references in Mahabharata where Brahmanas like Dronacharya, Kripa, and Asvathama fought. These dynamics of marginalization and empowerment of Dalits, Adiwasis as well as those born in low caste or who were uneducated in ancient Indian society are present noticeably in the *Mahabharata*. For example, Vyasa, the mythical composer of the *Mahabharata*, himself belonged to the marginalized community—being the dark-skinned illegitimate son of Satyawati, the daughter of a fisherman of the Nishada race.

In the Ekalavya episode and the circumstances surrounding it, all the expectations and duties of the traditional order of society are overturned and the world is turned upside down. The epic is forcing readers to think that *dharma* is not a hidebound and rigid doctrine whose pursuit and practice are confined to the two highest *varnas*. Anyone, even a *nishada* can uphold *dharma*; a Brahmin and a warrior can fall from the standards of their assigned *dharma*. This is a very radical suggestion in the epic. As Dr. Rudrangshu rightly said, "I would suggest that the epic is suggesting [in the Ekalavya episode] that ethical conduct—the pursuit and the practice of *dharma*—has nothing to do with birth" (10).

In the epic, Vidura is the embodiment of *dharma*, but he does not belong to an upper caste. His father is Vyasa, a half-caste, and his mother is a *sudra* maid. The god Dharma, under a curse, had to come to earth as a human and Dharma was born as Vidura (11)

The latter is thus Dharma and the principal practitioner of *dharma* throughout the tumultuous events of the epic. There are no transgressions on his part in word or deed. He never takes up the cause of violence and cruelty even as he watches events unfold.

Tribal and Marginal Communities

The Great Epic has left numerous landmarks in the region. The most remarkable aspect of the Mahabharata war was the recruitment by both the Pandavas and Kauravas of a veritable host of primitive tribes from jungles and inaccessible valleys, without discrimination, into their respective armies. Bands of fierce jungle tribes, known as *atavika* formed the bulk of the fighting forces on both sides (12). The epic duly acknowledged individual tribal warriors such as Eklavya (a Bhil) and Ghatotkacha (a Rakshasa) for their legendary courage and fighting skills.

Ghatotkacha is the son of Bhima and the giantess Hidimbi (sister of Hidimba). His maternal parentage made him half-rakshasa and gave him many magical powers such as the ability to fly which made him an important fighter in the Kurukshetra war, the climax of the epic. The *Kirātas* correspond broadly to the Indo-Mongoloids of the Northeast. •Prāgjyotiṣ a: founded by Naraka and his son Bhagadatta (who fights Arjuna in the Epic). Bhagadatta is a historical figure: he is mentioned in inscriptions, such as the

Nalandaseal of Bhaskaravarman. •After the war, Arjuna goes out to Manipura on a mission to placate the Nāgas and marries Ulūpī. •A tradition identifies Ghaṭotkacha, Bhīma's son from Hiḍimba, with the Kachhari kingdom in Assam (whose capital Dimapur was a corruption of "Hiḍimbapur"). •The Bodos have a tradition of having given Rukmini, a Kirāta woman, to Krishna. They claim Bhagadatta and Hiḍimba among their ancestors.

The epic displays an intimate knowledge of the different tribes in the different regions, as well as of the special fighting skills for which they were renowned. Bhishma instructed Yudhishthira (13) to recruit people in the various wings of the army after studying their particular modes of fighting. He expressed a preference for frontier peoples for handling different missiles, while the Gandhara, Sindhu, and Sauvira tribes were accomplished in fighting With nails and lances. The Usinaras were skilled in all weaponry, while the Easterners were adept in elephant-back

According to Sheldon Pollock, "The Mahabharata offers perhaps the most sustained study in world literature of the undecidability of conflicting moral claims – what the text itself repeatedly calls the 'subtlety' of the moral order..." (14)

The individuals at the center of the incidents mentioned above do not belong to the dominant castes. They are either of mixed caste origins—like Vyasa, Yuyutsu, and Vidura—or from lower castes, such as Ekalavya, a Nishada. The Mahabharata thus reflects the structure of a rigid Brahmanical society while simultaneously conveying a profound message: human action and achievement in ancient times often transcended narrow social discriminations rooted in caste and creed.

Conclusion

In the epic, marginalization—whether within the royal family, among upper castes, or within tribal communities—fades in significance when confronted by exceptional merit, remarkable personality, and strength of character. This timeless message of the Mahabharata, though rooted in ancient Indian society, retains its relevance in postcolonial times. The epic continues to exert a profound social and cultural influence, shaping and inspiring the dynamic responses and behaviors of modern *humanity*.

While the Mahabharata lays bare the operations of dominant ideologies, it also employs key episodes to challenge and invite readers to transcend those boundaries, even subverting them. The text suggests that birth and caste are no barriers to the practice of dharma or the upholding of honor, emphasizing the universal values of merit, character, and justice.

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